

REASONS BEHIND VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN IN INDIA

Mrs. Suresh Kumari

Assistant Professor in Law HIM CAPES Badhera (Una) H.P.

Violence against women has attained magnitude of a universal phenomenon resulting in more & more broken homes, physical & mental torture is an age-old social stigma, but the law alone can not curb their domestic affection. Even diverse can not do justice in many cases especially where the women is unemployed or not having any monetary gaining. The poor lady has not option, but to tolerate the torture beating, cruelty, humiliation and compromise with the *situation*¹ violence against women is also a manifestation of class oppression, Domestic violence, battering, dowry, rape, suicide are the *manifestation*² of gender inequalities wit the family system in our society, the responsibility to run the home and take care of children is that of women. Even where they are employed outside the home not only have they to work in office-both before going to and after returning from the office, but will have to carry out the household chores apart from attending to children & take care of visitor as long as there is no understanding and sharing of household work between men and women and the family is solely dependent on the women of the house, it is a bind of deprivation to the women of leisure or time for pursuit of other interest in addition to reducing the burden of *family*³.

The Indian Women is still not free, exploited sold commodity, liquidated without the law and held hostage by an exploitation *combination*³. These crime against women may have been declared deviant acts by the law of the land but society considers otherwise whenever a crime against a woman is committed, the judgment is predetermined the woman must be at fault. The society will always has an excuse to blame the woman and absolve the man. The argument ban forward shows social tolerance of crimes against *women*⁵.

Factors responsible violence against the women

There are factors responsible for violence against women.

- 1) Traditional societal norms of sexual inequality.
- 2) Lack of female leadership and lack of social movement.
- 3) Dependence of women.
- 4) Physical in capabilities.
- 5) Meek personality developed due to socialization process.

6) Loopholes in law and lack of legal protection.

- 1) Maya Majumdar: Protecting our women, Vol. I (2001) 337
- 2) Preeti Mishra Gender justice issue ombudsman—An effective A.D.R. Journal Section A.I.R. (2001) 150
- 3) Justice “Rajendra Babu”, third Shri Abella Satynarayan Memorial Endowment Lecture on Gender Justice Indian Prospective, Supreme Court Cases (2002, SSCCJ) 2-3
- 4) V.R. Krishna Iyer, women and the law in modern India, Religion law review Vol. VII (1998) 1
- 5) Maya Majumdar – Protecting our women Vol. I, (2001) 7

Traditional societal norms of sexual in equality

The traditional institutionalization of violence in different ways is a combined result of the normative structure. In the traditional set up, violence against women started almost at birth, its most extreme form being the culturally legitimized femicide through female infanticide although it was limited to the parts of Rajasthan and Gujarat (and was forbidden by British legislation introduced in 1877, specifically in these areas) a girl was usually made to feel unwelcome and undesirable, as well as inferior to her brothers and to all men in *general*⁶.

During school going age, both boys and girls given equal care and affection. However the differential treatment began by the age of six onwards girls were trained to be efficient housewife serving obedient, they could adjust at In-laws *family*⁷. The secondary status of women being with rise of the Kshatriya in India. Buddha, Mahavir, being Kshatriya intellectual gave women a secondary status in their religion. After the sixth century with the appearance of the Islamic and domination of the Afghans and the Mughal, the same pattern was *re-enforced*⁸

During the last decade the number of female children to male children in the youngest age group fell from 945 per 1000 males to 927 female per 1000 males as per data available there seems to be gender disparity depending on the location as the Northern state particularly (Punjab, Haryana, H.P.) seem to be more biased than the southern states. The sharpest decline for the age group of Zero to six years is observed in the northern state particularly in Punjab (793 female per 1000 male) and Haryana (820 females per 1000 males) These new figures point out that the use of new technology contributes to the gender composition. Due to the

wide spread use of this technology, inspite of the Indian Govt. has banned the sex determination before birth.

6) Shirin Kudchedar, Sabina AL-Issa, violence against women (1998) 20

1) Usha S. Kanher, Women and Socialization, (1987) 72

2) Indira J. Pariks, Indian women an Inner Dialogue (1989) 81-83

The female child in India is deprived from her right of an education. The number of girls dropping out of school for exceeds the boys because girls are expected to help at home. Either with household work like washing and cooking nearly 80% of the girls drop out from standards I to V out of the 100 girls that enroll in the first year of school only 42 reach class V among SC and ST many of those who live below poverty line only 19 of out of 100 girls reach class V⁹.

ii) Lack of female leadership and lack of social movement

Women participate in large number in social reforms movements in community based organization and none governmental organization not in mainstream politics. The documented forms of political participation of men and women emphasize women's lack of visibility in various spheres of political participation. Such as membership and leadership in political parties, the Govt. union and voting process among others in which women rarely *participate*⁹⁽ⁱ⁾. The number of women in leadership position at the local village, district and national level still not commensurate with their number in *society*¹⁰.

The Indian women movement in 1970 and early 1980 s was characterized by a broad ideological consensus on a number of issues and *approaches*¹¹. It was around 1970-1980 that women organized demonstration around to issue dowry and rape.

1) Women's participation in politics in India

Women's participation in politics instill not very impressive. The number of women politician is small as compared to men. The majority of women are indifferent to politics, this is clear in their low participation in voting, in public demonstration and in public debates.

9) Discrimination Against Girls In India [https:// www.en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/](https://www.en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/)

9 (i) Sangeeta Purushotm :- The empowerment of women in India (1988) 55

10) Maya Majumdar: Protecting our women Vol. III, 39

11) Is gender justice only a legal issue? Political stakes in UCC debates perspective economic and political weakly (March 1-8, 1997) 453

Whatever participation; it is mostly limited to women from the urban-elite groups. It is interesting that a higher voting percentage is found among rural and poor women, while the urban and the educated women show a poor polling turnout. Thus participation in voting can

not be regarded as a reliable indicator of political awareness women vote on the instructions of their men. In the recent election held in the country, none of the political parties put up as many candidates, and neither the Lok Sabha, the house of people nor any of the state legislatures reached anywhere near the 33% level. The number of women ministers is also very small. In 2012, India had a minimal percentage of 10.9% women elected representative in the national parliament, women turnout during India's 2014 parliamentary general elections was 65.63% compared to 67.09% turnout for men. India ranks 20th from the bottom in terms of representation of women in *parliament*¹².

ii) Women's Social Movements in India

The status of women has been the central concern of many reform movement before or after independence. Leaders of the Brahma Samaj & the Arya Samaj were concerned with issues like Sati, remarriage, divorce, female education, Purdha System, Pologamy and dowry, Raja Ram Mohan Roy played an important role in getting the Sati system abolished. Ishwar Chandra Vidya Sagar and Maharishi Karve pleaded for remarriage of widows. It may be said that women participation in movements has been in four major forms.

- 1) For social, economic and political rights of specific categories of people like tribal's, peasants and industrial workers.
- 2) For improvement in condition of work and autonomy to women.
- 3) For equal remuneration for work
- 4) In general social movements on issues affecting women & children like abortions adoption of children, sexual exploitation *etc*¹³.

12) participation in politics in India.

[http:// www.yourarticlelibrary.com/women's](http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/women's)

13) Women movements in India : Forms and main National Organizations

[http:// www.historydiscussion.net/essaye/womens-movement-in-india](http://www.historydiscussion.net/essaye/womens-movement-in-india)

DEPENDENCE OF WOMEN

The traditional Joint family system in male dominated women is considered inferior to dependent on and under subjugation of man, she is considered to be under the protection of man all through her life, under father in childhood, under husband in the youth and under son in the old *age*¹⁴. Sex linked division of work has prevailed in the Indian society since time immorial. Man was the bread winner, has to take up important rule earning a living for the

family and hence appropriate role in the outside society. He keeps control of the family finances and has a right to family inheritance; this has given him power and authority over women. Even when women participate in earning a living, it is rated as subsidiary and subordinate to them to that of *men*¹⁵.

The practice of child marriage, Sati infanticide of new born girl, prohibition of female education and polygamy marriage, slavery, Purdha System and Dowry System, all these prescribed by the society left the women weak and dependent on men from the time of their birth to death.

Physical In Capabilities :-

Women have always been treated as an object of gross and severe violence at the hands of men. The biological weakness of a woman makes her an easy prey particularly to physical domination. She is often a victim of physical violence not only outside her home but also within her home. No place is safe, not the home, the campus in the workplace or the street. No age is safe whatever infants or old women. Mass violence against the weaker section of society, whether on the basis of class, race, religion or gender frequently takes the form of mass rape and gang rape of the women of targeted *groups*¹⁷.

Crime against women reported every two minutes.

Crimes against women have more than doubled over the past ten years. As many as 2:24

- 14) Raka Ray, Field of protest (2000), 13
- 15) Usha Kunher: Women and Socialization (1987) 4
- 16) Maya Majumdar: Protecting our women (2001) Vol. III, 363-364
- 17) R.K. Bag, Domestic Violence and Crime Against Women, Criminal Justice Response in India, Journal of the Indian Law Institute Vol. III (April to Dec. 1997 N2-4) 361

million crimes against women were reported over the past decade 26 crimes against women are reported every hour or one complaint every two minutes, reveals on India spend analyses based on the last decade's data (National crime records bureau) 10 cases of cruelty by husband and relatives are reported every hour across the country followed by cases of assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty, kidnapping and abduction and *rape*¹⁸.

Meek personality developed due to socialization process.

The Hindu religiosity considered sons essential in the family because son alone could offer oblations of the departed ancestors and save the demises ancestors from suffering the spell of hell in "put" or "pung" on the other hand, the daughter could not perform any of the spiritual ceremonies and rites and therefore, necessarily inferior to a *son*¹⁹. We have grown up with

stories of Sita and Savitri, which applaud the self sacrifice made by women for the greater good of other. A recent research study published by A.C. Nielsen, titled women of tomorrow reports that women in India (87%) are most stressed/pressured for time. Confidence survey validates the working mothers constantly feel a tug of *war*²⁰.

The factors lie in the socio-cultural aspects, which demands also scrutiny. The socialization process that is followed in the common household faulty. The girls are taught to remain silent even if they are abused, molested and tortured in their own household for the sake of family pride. Even they can not choose their partners as it is imposed by the male members in most of the cases. So the socialization process develop a culture of silence among the women.

18) crime against women reported every two minutes

[http://www.indiaspend.com\(Sep.4,2015\)](http://www.indiaspend.com(Sep.4,2015))

19) Padma: Gender Justice standard emergent in Indian law, Supreme Court Journal, Vol. 3, 1999

20) <http://www.womenswed.in/articles/career-confidence-india-women>

Loopholes in the laws and lack of legal protection.

In India women are guaranteed equal freedom, opportunity and protection by the constitution and several legislation but there continue to be victims of domestic violence, family violence, violence in the community and at work place, illiteracy, ignorance, lack of awareness, poverty added with traditional oppressions and customs, place the Indian women at uneven status. The laws enacted for the protection of women suffer from various shortcomings. The enforcement of these laws is so poor that the offenders see to have lost all fear of *authority*²².

Ineffective legal machinery

The police is the first agency for the administration of criminal justice and is considered to be first line of defense. In India police inefficiency, corruption, connivance with guilty and the police politician nexus have been the major cause of crimes against women police mostly fail to protect women from being attacked criminally assaulted, humiliated, dishonoured and otherwise victimized²³.

Increasing graph of crime.

In 2015, over 34,600 cases of rape have been reported across the country with Madhya Pradesh and Delhi topping the infamous list of states and union territories respectively. Nearly 3.27 lakh cases of crimes against women were reported across the country 1.3 lakh were sexual offences and the sexual offences cases included rape, attempt to commit rape, assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty and insult to modesty of *women*²⁴.

More than 50% case of human trafficking involved minors & close 90% of them were girls trafficked to be forced into prostitution in 2015 according to the NCRB data for 2015 out of 6,877 cases of human trafficking in the country. 3,490 (51%) involved children of these 3,087 (88.5%) were cases registered U/s 366 AC procreation of girls to force her into sex) of the IPC 1860.

22) Fatima Ehtesham Siddique and Sarla Ranganathan women and humans rights (2001) 123

23) Maya Majumdar, Protecting our women (2001) (Vol. 1) 17 , 18-19

24) National Crime Record Bureau data 2015, express.com/updatedAug.30,2016

According to the NCRB data, Assam, West Bengal, Bihar and Haryana alone accounted for 85% of child trafficking cases in country.

Sexual offences along with kidnapping and abduction constituted 81% of all cases of crimes against children in 2015 ²⁶

The graph of the crime against women continued to show upward trend even in the year 2016 in the commercial capital of the country as the law and order enforcement authorities failed to control the crimes ²⁷.

CONCLUSION:-

It is pertinent to mention that the cancer of gender inequality plagues in Indian society and considered as the root cause of perpetuity of violence against women. Violence like rape, dowry related abuse, sex-selection and male preference continue unabated in India. The most important thing that the state has failed to introduce the definition of safety from violence from a woman's perspective.

26) National crime records bureau-data 2015 [http:// Indian.express.com/article/explained/](http://Indian.express.com/article/explained/)

27) [http:// www.dailyexcelsior.com/crime-women-increased2016](http://www.dailyexcelsior.com/crime-women-increased2016).

THE BIBLIOGRAPHY :-

BOOKS

Maya Majumdar: Protecting our women, Vol. I (2001) 337

Preeti Mishra Gender justice issue ombudsman—An effective A.D.R. Journal Section A.I.R. (2001) 150

Justice “Rajendra Babu”, third Shri Abella Satynarayan Memorial Endowment Lecture on Gender Justice Indian Prospective, Supreme Court Cases (2002, SSCCJ) 2-3

V.R. Krishna Iyer, women and the law in modern India, Religion law review Vol. VII (1998) 1

Shirin Kudchedar, Sabina AL-Issa, violence against women (1998) 20

Usha S. Kanher, Women and Socialization, (1987) 72

Indira J. Pariks, Indian women an Inner Dialogue (1989) 81-83

Sangeeta Purushotm :- The empowerment of women in India (1988) 55

Maya Majumdar: Protecting our women Vol. III, 39

Economic and Political Weekly (March 1-8, 1997) 453

Women movements in India : Forms and main National Organizations

Raka Ray, Field of protest (2000), 13

R.K. Bag, Domestic Violence and Crime Against Women, Criminal Justice Response in India, Journal of the Indian Law Institute Vol. III (April to Dec. 1997 N2-4) 361

WEB SITES:-

[https:// www.en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/](https://www.en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/)

[http:// www.yourarticlelibrary.com/women's](http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/women's)

[http:// www.historydiscussion.net/essaye/womens-movement-in-india](http://www.historydiscussion.net/essaye/womens-movement-in-india)

[http://www.indiaspend.com\(Sep.4,2015\)](http://www.indiaspend.com(Sep.4,2015))

<http://www.womenswed.in/articles/career-confidence-india-women>

[http:// www.dailyexcelsior.com/crime-women-increased2016.](http://www.dailyexcelsior.com/crime-women-increased2016)